

Psychological Safety

Survey Flow

Standard: Welcome page (1 Question)
Standard: Screening Questions (2 Questions)
Standard: Demographic (6 Questions)
Standard: Project and Team (10 Questions)
Standard: Measuring psychological safety (1 Question)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership (5 Questions)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team (2 Questions)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team 2 (2 Questions)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership and Team (1 Question)
Standard: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Individuals 1 (2 Questions)
Standard: Effect of Psychological Safety (8 Questions)
Standard: Moderating variables (5 Questions)

Page Break

Start of Block: Welcome page

WP

Thanks for taking time to participate in our survey. You have either participated on the prescreening or on the pilot versions of this survey. You have been invited to participate because you meet the study criteria. Please, answer every question carefully.

In this research project, we aim at understanding agile teams approaches to admitting mistakes, taking initiatives, talking about problems, and helping each other and how doing so contributes to achieving software quality. Your participation is anonymous, and the survey should take 20 mins to complete.

This research project is led by Adam Alami, assistant professor at Aalborg University, Denmark, in collaboration with Mansooreh Zahedi, assistant professor at the University of Melbourne and Oliver Krancher, associate professor at the IT University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Your data will be used to carry out research for scholarly publication. As part of the publication process, the data will be shared in anonymized form, which does not reveal the identity of the survey participants and their organisations.

We thank you again for helping us to understand better how agile teams help each others and work collaboratively to achieve better software quality.

Sincerely,

Adam Alami, Mansooreh Zahedi and Oliver Krancher

Page Break

End of Block: Welcome page

Start of Block: Screening Questions

ProlificID What is your Prolific ID?

Page Break

Location_1 Where are you currently located?

▼ United States ... Other

Page Break

End of Block: Screening Questions

Start of Block: Demographic

Age_2 What is your age?

- 30 years or younger
 - 31 - 40 years
 - 41 - 50 years
 - Over 51 years old
-

Gender_3 How do you identify your gender?

- Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary / third gender
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe (please specify below)
-

Page Break

Role_4 What is your role in your software development team?

- Software engineer
 - Senior software engineer
 - Software developers (including Front End, Back End developers, etc.)
 - Tech Lead
 - Solution architect
 - Quality assurance engineer
 - Quality assurance analyst
 - QA Lead
 - DevOps Engineer
 - Release Engineer
 - Other (please specify below)
-

Page Break

Experience_5 How many years of your experience do you have in software development and/or software quality assurance?

- Less than 3 years
 - 3 - 5 years
 - 6 - 8 years
 - 9 - 11 years
 - More than 12 years
-

AgileExp_6 How many years of your experience has been in agile teams?

- Less than 3 years
 - 3 - 5 years
 - 6 - 8 years
 - 9 - 11 years
 - More than 12 years
-

Page Break

Education_7 What is your education level?

- Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - PhD
 - Other (please specify below)
-

End of Block: Demographic

Start of Block: Project and Team

Team_8 Throughout this survey, we will be asking questions regarding your current team. In all questions, we use "team", "my team" or "our team" to refer to your current team. Please, answer all the questions in the context of your current team. Do you understand this requirement?

- Yes, I understand this requirement
- No, I do not understand this requirement

Page Break

AgileMethod_9 What agile method do you use in your team?

- Scrum
 - XP
 - Kanban
 - SAFe
 - Other (please specify below)
-

TeamSize_10 How many people are usually on your team? (i.e., in average considering team members leave and new members come quite often)

Page Break

ProjectScope_11 Please, briefly describe the scope of the project you are currently working on:

Page Break

MultiFunc_12 To what extent do you agree with the following statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
In my team, we have people with all the skills (e.g., front-end, back-end, database, operations, business users) that are required for the project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

SoftDev_13 What type of product/software do you develop in your team?

- Custom development
 - Implementation of software packages/COTS
 - Maintenance/enhancement of existing system(s)
 - Other (specify below)
-

WorkingTogether_14 How long has your team been working together in your current team?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 – 2 years
- 3 – 4 years
- More than 4 years

Page Break

InHouseOutsource_15 Are you an in-house software team (i.e., you develop software for your own organisation) or an outsourced software team (i.e., you develop software for client that is another organisation)?

- In-house
- Outsourced
- Other (specify below)
-

Colocated_16 How often are the members of your team colocated (i.e., same office or same office floor)?

- Always
- 3-4 days per week
- 1-2 days per week
- Less than 1 day per week
-

MultipleTeams_17 Do you work in a project that involves multiple teams?

- No
- Yes
-

Page Break

End of Block: Project and Team

Start of Block: Measuring psychological safety

PS_18 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
If you make mistakes on my team, is it often held against you	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my team can bring up problems and tough issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People on my team sometimes reject others based on the ideas they propose	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is safe to take a risk (e.g., experiment with a new technology, propose initiatives, raise difficult issues, disclose own knowledge gaps) on my team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel comfortable asking my team members for help	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No one on my team would deliberately act in a way that	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

undermine
my efforts

Working with
members of
my team, my
unique skills
and talents
are valued
and utilized

Page Break

End of Block: Measuring psychological safety

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership

Leadership_19 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... is resolute about psychological safety in our team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... is determined to promote a work environment where people dare to take risks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... accepts that failure can occur when we try out new things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Leadership_20 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... listens to our needs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... wants to hear about our concerns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... is willing to listen to our suggestions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Leadership_21 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... is supportive of us	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... provides help with everything we need to deliver our projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... always treats us with respect	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... strongly supports us doing our work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Leadership_22 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

Our leadership ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... “walk the talk” when it comes to taking risk and accepting failure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... “practice what they preach” when it comes to psychological safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... follows through on the values of psychological safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... are role models in terms of taking risks and accepting failures	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... words are well aligned with their actions when it comes to admitting mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

AttentionCheck_23 Please, indicate your agreement with the following statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I'm passionate about my job. Please, answer "Strongly agree"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team

Autonomy_24 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In our team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we are responsible for deciding how to organize our work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we decide how to achieve our goals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make the decisions regarding the technical solutions with no interferences from management or our stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make the decisions regarding the tasks' estimation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... In our team we are allowed to change our processes in order to improve our performance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we have the freedom to make decisions on architectural design	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

decisions,
choice of
technology
and tools

Page Break

DecisionMaking_25 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In our team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we engage in constructive discussions to make our decisions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... each team member's voice counts when decisions are made	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we make decisions based on the best arguments that team members contribute	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we aim to reach consensus when we make our decisions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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SlackTime_26 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

In our team, we have ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... time that we can use for activities beyond developing new functionality (e.g., technical improvements, refactoring, process improvements).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... enough time available to ensure we can meet deadlines even if unexpected problems arise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... no problems obtaining sufficient time for activities that do not immediately produce customer value (e.g., technical improvements, refactoring, process improvements)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

SafetyNet_27 Our use of engineering practices (e.g., test automation, continuous integration) ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... reduces the likelihood that something goes wrong	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... gives us the confidence that we can change code without breaking the software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... makes us confident that we notice mistakes before they turn into big problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Team 2

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership and Team

NoBlame_28 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In our team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we never blame each other for underperforming, instead we coach each other to improve	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... ... we do not blame each other for mistakes but see them as an opportunity for improvement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our leadership, including team leader and middle management, do not blame individuals for mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Leadership and Team

Start of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Individuals 1

Openness_29 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

People in our team ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... are open to criticism and feedback from their peers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... always welcome new ideas and initiatives put forward by their peers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... do not reject ideas based on the individual who proposed it but based on the strength and the soundness of the idea	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... accept the rejection of new ideas when the rejection is based on strong arguments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... accept the rejection of ideas when they fail to convince team members with their arguments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

SpeakingUp_30 To what extent do you agree with these statements:

In my team ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... people always raise the concerns they have	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... people talk about problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... people share their opinions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... people point out quality problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

End of Block: Antecedents of Psychological Safety - Individuals 1

Start of Block: Effect of Psychological Safety

AdmittingMistakes_31 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Members of my team talk about the mistakes they make related to software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my team do not get blamed by their team members for mistakes related to software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I admit my mistakes related to software quality to my team because there are no repercussions, instead we deal with the situation constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When mistakes related to software quality are admitted by a team member, we deal with the situation constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

AdmittingMistakes_32 What type of mistakes related to software quality have you experienced and admitted to your team in the past? Can you share two examples?

Page Break

LearningMistakes_33 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
As a team, when we admit software quality mistakes, we learn from our mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Past software quality mistakes usually become a point of reference in our team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When past software quality mistakes become a point of reference in our team, we avoid similar mistakes in the future	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Helping_34 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

In my team ...

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we find it very important to help each others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often help each other on software quality-related issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often ask for help from our peers to improve the quality of our code	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often ask for help from our peers to resolve defects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we share knowledge related to software quality to help each other to improve the quality of our work when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

ProblemSolving_35 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
As a team, we collectively solve problems when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When there are tough problems to solve in our team, we analyze them jointly	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
As a team, we help each other to solve software quality problems (e.g., resolving defects, making design decisions, coding decisions)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

AttentionCheck_36 This is a simple test, when asked about your favorite city you must select Casablanca. What is your favorite city?

- Paris
- Casablanca
- Venice
- New York
- Sydney

Page Break

TakingInitiatives_37 To what extent do you agree with this statement:

In my team ...	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
... we often propose software quality initiatives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often propose software quality-related experiments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... we often try out new things to increase software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... prior to experimenting with new ideas, we collectively assess the potential risks to help us decide	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my team often make suggestions for improving software quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

TakingInitiatives_38 What type of experiments and initiatives related to software quality have you conducted in your team in the past? Can you share two examples?

Page Break

End of Block: Effect of Psychological Safety

Start of Block: Moderating variables

Coaching_39 In your team, how often do you coach each other on software quality related issues?

- Never
 - Sometimes
 - About half the time
 - Most of the time
 - Always
-

PairProgramming_40 In your team, how often do you use pair programming to help each other?

- Never
 - Sometimes
 - About half the time
 - Most of the time
 - Always
-

Page Break

Role_41 What is your role in your software development team?

- Software engineer
 - Senior software engineer
 - Software developers (including Front End, Back End developers, etc.)
 - Tech Lead
 - Solution architect
 - Quality assurance engineer
 - Quality assurance analyst
 - QA Lead
 - DevOps Engineer
 - Release Engineer
 - Other (please specify below)
-

Page Break

ProjectScope_42 Please, briefly describe the scope of the project you are currently working on:

Technologies_43 **For software engineers:** What programming languages, software development/programming frameworks, and other programming technologies you are currently using in your team?

For QAs: What quality assurance processes you are currently using in your team?

End of Block: Moderating variables
